

SUBJECT, TASKS AND CONTENT OF STUDYING THE BASICS OF MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION

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Annotation: mastering the theory and practice of military-patriotic education of young people, comprehensively preparing them for military service, fulfilling their duty to protect their homeland-the Republic of Uzbekistan-is one of the important tasks of pedagogical communities of educational institutions.

To successfully solve this task, the subject "fundamentals of military-patriotic education", which is being taught in the specialty of military education, will help closely. Methodological and ideological-theoretical foundations of youth militaristic education as a subject of study of the subject" fundamentals of military-patriotic education", the system of military-patriotic education in an educational institution, the organization of spiritual-political,

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The main tasks of the foundations of military-patriotic education are as follows:

first of all, it is inextricably linked with other subjects taught at a higher educational institution, to educate students in a national and international spirit, to ensure that they are always armed with weapons for the protection of their homeland;

secondly, to develop the qualities of a pedagogical teacher in students who are actively conscious, hardworking, capable of educating a young generation ready for courage and heroism for the motherland; thirdly, to arm students with theoretical-practical knowledge of military-patriotic education, to organize and conduct education in them, to form skills and qualifications, and educational work in general secondary education During the study, each student must independently write 4-5 lectures on the topic of military-patriotism, participate in leadership work for any circle on the basics of military training in high

schools. The subject "fundamentals of military-patriotic education" closely helps future military training leaders in the preparation of a worthy young generation at a high level, ready for the protection of the motherland.

The problem of educating the growing younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and raising them as mature citizens is one of the important tasks facing our state and society. The rapid volatility of the political situation in the world, the peculiarities of socio-political life, our state demand an inexhaustible increase in defense capabilities, systematic preparation of the younger generation for the protection of the motherland. Raising young people in the spirit of military patriotism, respect for our national traditions and values, raising a spiritually mature and physically healthy harmonious generation, reliably protecting their rights and interests, interest and active participation of young people in the military in the large-scale reforms carried out in our Armed Forces is one of the most important tasks today.

Patriotic education is a complex and multifaceted activity of its nature. As one of the most important values of society, it covers social, political, spiritual-moral, cultural, historical and other characteristics within its content. Patriotism is an expression of a person's high emotional-spiritual attitude towards his homeland and is a component of a person's spiritual wealth. True patriotism always manifests itself as an integral unit of spiritual, civil responsibility and social activity of a person and serves as a driving force in human activities in the interests of the motherland.

The patriotic character can be in relation to its people, its nationality and the society and state in which a person lives. These characteristics should unite and form a single holistic feature of patriotism, since every responsible citizen of Uzbekistan understands perfectly well that the interests of his family, nationality are inextricably linked with the interests of other nationalities and nationalities of our country.

The patriotism of the citizens of Uzbekistan represents a sense of responsibility for his "small Homeland", nationality, as well as for the whole country, for the whole of Uzbekistan. Looking at the history of our motherland, our nation of late, accused of its freedom, independence, has always been under its protection. Spiritual and spiritual training of Citizens for the protection of the Motherland is one of the socio-political directions of ensuring the military independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today, in order to entrust the defender of the Fatherland with the management of Modern Combat Equipment and weapons, he must first understand in depth why, for what purposes, he is

doing this. It is necessary to present to each student jonajan Uzbekistan and his family, friends, neighborhoods, rural"U-cities" with glorious history, great culture and immortal traditions. So, it is necessary to explain to readers that these riches - family, friends and Homeland-should be protected by weapons when the time comes.

In order to skillfully protect the Motherland on threatening days, it is necessary to prepare for this from youth. Therefore, patriotic education is carried out in public places during the school period, and it will also be interesting for students. To do this, teachers with such a responsible and honorable task must have thoroughly mastered its advanced modern theory and practice in order to carry out this upbringing. The place of our Armed Forces is constantly occupied by young people. These young people need to master modern combat techniques and weapons in a short time and learn to use them skillfully.

The success of a young soldier in the armed forces will largely depend on the goal-oriented work of the military training system. Patriotic education is a purposeful and constant pedagogical influence on the consciousness, psyche, will and physical fitness of the younger generation. Patriotic education of the younger generation has always been one of the most important tasks of the modern educational system, since childhood and adolescence are considered the most optimal period for the formation of a feeling of love for the motherland.

The tasks performed by the military-patriotic education system determine its structure. Organizationally, the components of the military-patriotic education system are moral-spiritual, historical, patriotic, military-technical and physical training. To create a system of training the defender of the fatherland and increase its effectiveness, it is important to know the goals and objectives of training military patriotism, as well as one of the complex qualities of a person as a shaylik for the defense of the Fatherland. Nevertheless, the idea of belonging to the defense of the motherland does not reveal all the complex sides of this quality, the character of dressing. This means that even if the motherland risks its life, it is impossible to develop a sense of protection, to replace the formation of Special positive qualities in a person's character.

That is why it is necessary to have a holistic idea of the homeland in order to create a whole educational process that ensures the protection of the motherland. In this regard, it is necessary that the organizers of military-patriotic education have a deep knowledge of general pedagogy and psychology, as well as military pedagogy and psychology. Because, as these disciplines say,

the defense of the motherland manifests a whole complex of human qualities, such as shyness, faith, emotion, simplicity, strong will, Physical Fitness and military skill. All these qualities are inextricably linked with each other, together they form a holistic structure of the shaylik for the protection of the motherland, and this is one of the main qualities of a person in patriotic education, the tasks of each direction are carried out in three ways:

- introducing the reader to moral characteristics such as basic affection, love, care, truth and beauty;
- to understand the meaning of life and humanity to the reader, to activate his inner personal psyche;
- formation of its activities and creative approach to the world around it

The purpose of military-patriotic education in secondary schools: - the formation of skills in students to develop civil responsibility, patriotism, as well as other important knowledge and skills and actively apply them in various aspects of society's life. Assignments:

1. Formation of a system of legal regulation in the field of military-patriotic education in secondary schools;
2. Introduction of the most effective methods for the formation of civil-patriotic qualities of a person;
3. Formation of a system of activities aimed at the development of patriotism by involving students in practical activities;
4. Formation of a positive attitude towards military and public service in students;
5. Creating conditions for students to manifest themselves and adapt to social life;
6. Ensuring social cooperation of the school with public associations and state organizations in the field of military-patriotic education; are conditions for the implementation of the goals and objectives of military-patriotic education, such as civil responsibility, recognition of the high social significance of patriotism and loyalty to the motherland.

Also, in the implementation of practical activities in the field of military-patriotic education, science, humanization, democratization, cultural-historical heritage of Uzbekistan, its spiritual values and traditions, continuity in youth education, variety of forms, methods and tools that ensure the effectiveness of upbringing, its orientation towards education. development of the abilities and qualities of the individual on the basis of an individual approach to each;

The implementation of these principles in the process of military-patriotic education of young people serves to develop in them a real interest in the state and military service, preparation for the worthy protection of the motherland.

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